

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Research Article

A Study on Knowledge, Attitude and Practice About Self-Medication Among Rural Population of Kalaburagi District

Bhosale Abhilekh*, Patti Sri Harsha Vardhan, Siddaling Phoolar, Sagar Reddy, Vishwanath M. Jeevangi

Rajiv Memorial Education Society's College of Pharmacy, Kalburagi-585102.

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 25 Oct 2025

Keywords:

Self-Medication, World Health Organization, Rural population, Over the Counter, Adverse Drug Reactions

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.17430492

ABSTRACT

Background: The World Health Organization (WHO) defines self-medication (SM) as the use of drugs to treat self-diagnosed conditions or the continued use of prescribed drugs without consultation. **Aim & Objectives:** This study aimed to assess the knowledge, attitude, and practice (KAP) of self-medication in the rural population of Kalaburagi district before and after an educational intervention. It also aimed to identify commonly self-treated conditions and preferred medications. **Materials And Methods:** A six-month, community-based, prospective educational study was conducted using a structured questionnaire. Data was collected before and after the distribution of educational leaflets. A post-test was conducted 14 days after the intervention. Statistical analysis was performed using IBM SPSS 25.0 with paired t-test applied for significance. **Results:** Of the 247 participants, 145 (58.7%) were male, and 113 (45.8%) were aged 21–40 years. Labourers formed the majority occupation (25.9%). The mean knowledge score (65.1%) showed significant improvement post-intervention. **Conclusion:** The study found that the rural population had inadequate knowledge of self-medication. Many participants believed SM is unsafe during pregnancy and for all age groups. Post-intervention, there was a significant improvement in KAP scores. The habit of checking expiry dates before use was noted. Educational efforts effectively enhanced awareness and safe practices.

INTRODUCTION

The World Health Organization (WHO) has defined self-medication as the practice whereby individuals treat their ailments and conditions with

medicines that are approved and available without prescription, and which are safe and effective when used as directed.¹ Individuals around the globe will, in general, treat the ailment, practically half either wait for the problem to run its course or utilize a home cure.²

***Corresponding Author:** Bhosale Abhilekh

Address: Rajiv Memorial Education Society's College of Pharmacy, Kalburagi-585102.

Email ✉: lekhabhi2000@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Medicines for self-medication are often called Non - Prescription or Over the Counter (OTC) drugs and are available without a doctor's prescription through pharmacies. Self - medication can readily relieve acute medical problems. It can save time spent in waiting to see a doctor and maybe economical also³. Self-medication is an important aspect in health-care delivery system.¹ The prevalence of self-treatment ranges from 0.1% to 27% in Europe and in the USA, which is much lower than developing countries. In India, the reported prevalence of self-medication is very high⁴, leading to 2.9 – 3.7% causes of death due to drug-drug interaction⁵ young generation have more positive attitude toward self-treatment, which is serious matter of concern⁴. In 60-80% of economically poor countries, the health-related problems are treated through self-medication as lower cost method.⁶ In developing countries like India not only OTC drugs, even prescription only medicines (POM) are also easily accessible without prescriptions in pharmacy outlets⁷. More than 50% people are taking drugs without a doctor's advice. In order to tackle this problem, the governments of all the developing countries have promulgated guidelines to prevent self-medication. Each and every drug that is registered to the concerned drug authorities must be strictly monitored for sale and prescription. Health department and drug regulatory authority should follow the WHO guidelines for drug prescription and dispensing.⁸ College going undergraduate student practice self-medication due to influencing advertisement media or social media.⁹ This is a threatening trend in young generation leading to improper diagnosis, drug interactions, adverse effects, poly pharmacy etc. and tends to endanger their lives because of these practices.⁹ Commonly self-medicated drugs worldwide, with over 50% purchased and used without a prescription.¹⁰ In line with Rather antibiotic SM constitutes internationally the most common and obvious

contributing factor of antibiotic-resistant pathogens.¹⁰ Now self-medication has led to increased bacterial resistance, failure in optimal treatment, unintentional and intentional poisonings, drug market disruption, financial loss, and \ increasing per capita of drugs consumption in the community (Hughes et al., 2001).¹¹ Medicines are responsible for 26% of intoxication recorded in the country in 2005, where only 590 cases were a result of self-medication. In a self-care context when there is need for medicines to the patient, the clinical pharmacist has a key role in assisting to identify the best involvement. This may include transfer to another health professional (general physician), suggesting a different non-pharmacological therapy, helping to choose an OTC medicine that is safe and effective, and ensuring that it is used correctly by patient. Therefore, responsible self-medication encourages the rational use of medicines.¹² Most of the self-medication drugs are from allopathic system but drugs from other systems are also used. Strict legislation with regard to accessibility to these drugs and educating the community on self-medication is essential for effective use of medicines required.¹³ Due to restricted health facilities, high cost, and long waiting hours, people tend to prefer self-treatment⁴ for self-recognized disorder or symptoms or the intermittent or continued use of medication prescribed by the physician for chronic or recurring disease or symptoms¹⁴. The condition is worst in rural or distant corners, where the people are deprived socially, economically, and educationally and illiterate with inadequate health facilities.¹² About 25% visit a specialist or utilize physician recommended medication recently got for a similar condition. The staying 25% go to the OTC prescriptions.² Although, OTC drugs are intended to be used as self-medication and are of established efficacy and safety but their inappropriate use due to lack of knowledge of their side effects and drug

interactions could have a serious consequence, especially in special population groups such as children, elderly, pregnant, and lactating mothers.¹² Self-medication involves the potential to do good as well as cause harm¹⁵. Although the practice of self-medication is inevitable, as the first line of contact in purchasing the OTC drugs.¹⁴ A Pharmacist can play a multidisciplinary approach to the promotion of the rational use of medicines by providing proper information, and instruction regarding the adverse drug reactions, dosage schedule of drugs to the patients, warning them about the unwanted effects and preventing abuse in patients.¹⁶ However, people should be properly educated about the practice of self-medication in order to prevent the harmful effects caused by the practice. The increasing self-medication will require more and better education of both the public and health professionals to avoid the complications arising from this practice.¹⁷

Conditions Treated By SM:

Headache, body ache, cough, cold, constipation, loose motion, acidity, generalized weakness, insomnia, fever, skin infections, joint pain, burns, menstrual pain, insect bite.

Common Medicines Used For SM:

Analgesics, antipyretics, antacids, antidiarrheal, antiallergic, antiemetics, antibiotics, vitamins, eye drops, ear drops, nasal drops, skin ointment, protein preparations.

Advantages Of SM:

- ☛ It helps to prevent and treat symptoms and ailments that don't require a doctor.
- ☛ Patient gets immediate relief; this reduces the pressure of medical services where health care services are not available and insufficient.

- ☛ Reduces economic burden and time regarding health care of the people.

- ☛ SM is first option for minor illness. In treatment of minor illness problems are self-limited, so SM is used.

Disadvantages Of SM:

Once medicines are entering human body, get absorbed rapidly. At the same time medicines gets sold rapidly through a powerful marketing and have no or less control over medicine. They are used and miss used and over used for different type of illness.

E.g:-1) Taking pain killers for long time without consultation of doctor and without knowing the cause of headache.

2) Paracetamol is antipyretic and analgesic which is used in large doses can cause liver problems (toxicity).

The major problem or disadvantages of SM is emergence of human pathogen resistance micro-organisms worldwide particularly in developing countries, where antibiotics are often

used and available without prescription. Its irrational use increases the risk of ADR's and person may develop resistance to particular antibiotics, hypersensitivity of drug withdrawal symptoms and temporary masking of disease can delay correct diagnosis.¹⁷

Need For Study

- Generally rural population have inadequate knowledge regarding the proper usage of medication.
- This study was planned because self-medication not only cause delay in actual

treatment but also further lead to misdiagnosis and drug interactions which could be fatal. It is now felt that the overall drug use situation needs to be assessed and educational should be given to have significant impact on knowledge in concern with proper usage of medications.

- By considering the above factors we have carried out the study on “Knowledge, Attitude & Practice about Self-Medication among rural population of Kalaburagi District”.

Aim & Objectives

Aim:

- To assess the Knowledge, Attitude and Practice about Self-Medication in rural population of Kalaburagi District.

Objectives:

- To assess the Knowledge, Attitude and Practice of Self-Medication in rural population by means of questionnaire (before intervention).
- To assess the Knowledge, Attitude and Practice of Self-Medication in rural population by means of questionnaire (after intervention).
- To assess impact of Self-Medication.
- To identify the most common conditions preferred for Self-Medication among rural population.
- To identify the most common medications preferred for Self-Medication among rural population.

METHODOLOGY

Plan Of the Study

Study Design: - Community based prospective educational study.

Source Of Data: -

1. Informed consent form.
2. Self-structured questionnaire.

Inclusion Criteria: - The data was collected among rural population of age ≥ 18 yrs of Kalaburagi District.

Exclusion Criteria: - Health care professionals, psychiatric patients and who are not present for posttest were excluded from the study.

Sample Size: - 247 subjects.

Duration Of Study: - The study was conducted for a period of 06 months. (March to August 2024).

Study Site: - Study was carried out in rural population of Kalaburagi District.

Study Procedure

A community based prospective educational study was conducted among the rural population in Kalaburagi District to assess the Knowledge, Attitude and Practice of Self-Medication. The study was initiated after the approval from Institutional Review Board (IRB) and was conducted for a period of six months. During this study, 247 people were interviewed and those fulfilling the inclusion criteria were enrolled into the study. The subjects who were willing to participate in the study were provided with informed consent form which was duly signed by them. After obtaining the consent, face to face interviews were conducted using questionnaire. Questionnaire is a predesigned proforma which includes patient demographic details (Name, age,

sex, occupation etc.). In our study, we have included total 30 questions. Out of which, Knowledge based questions were 10, Attitude were 10 questions and Practice were 10 questions. The participants were then given brief information about Self-Medication, its advantages & disadvantages. Then Knowledge, Attitude and Practice towards the medications were assessed. Drug and disease details were also collected. Two weeks after pre-test, all the participants were educated regarding Self-Medication by providing information leaflets. Post-test has been conducted after 14 days of education by means of same questionnaire. Statistical data was analyzed by IBM SPSS 25.0 version software. Collected data were spread on excel sheet and master chart was prepared. Through the master chart, tables and graphs were constructed. For quantitative data analysis, paired t- test was applied for statistical significance. If P-value was less than 0.05 it was considered as significant.

RESULTS

In the present study, 247 subjects were participated, all the participants were further subjected to statistical analysis with nil dropouts.

I. Demographic data

The selected subjects were categorized as per their gender i.e. male and female with following data.

Table No.1: Gender wise distribution of participants

Gender	Number of participants	Percentage
Males	145	58.7
Females	102	41.3
Total	247	100.0

Bar diagram represents gender wise distribution of participants

Figure no 1: Bar diagram represents gender wise distribution of participants

Furthermore, the consents were grouped into 4 major groups of 20 years gap interval and 18-20 as well as > 60 years.

Table No.2: Age wise distribution of rural population (participants)

Age in years	Number of participants	Percentage
18—20	26	10.5
21—40	113	45.8

41—60	83	33.6
61—80	25	10.1
Total	247	100.0
Mean ± SD	39.52 ± 15.37	

Bar diagram represents age wise distribution of rural population (participants)

Figure no 2: Bar diagram represents age wise distribution of rural population (participants)

The participants were also categorized based on their occupation i.e. Job holders, Housewife, Farmers, Labours, Students, Unemployed

Occupation	Number of participants	Percentage
Job holders	45	18.2
House wife	40	16.2
Farmers	49	19.8
Labours	64	25.9
Students	31	12.6
Unemployed	18	7.3
Total	247	100.0

Table No. 3 Occupation wise distribution of participants

Bar diagram represents occupation wise distribution of participants

Figure no 3: Bar diagram represents occupation wise distribution of participants

Details of distribution of participants according to marital status.

Married	175	70.9
Unmarried	72	29.1
Total	247	100.0

Table No.4: Marital status wise distribution of participants

Marital status	Number of participants	Percentage
----------------	------------------------	------------

Pie chart presents marital status wise distribution of participants

Figure no 4: Pie chart presents marital status wise distribution of participants

Details of distribution of participants according to their income.

6000—10000	61	24.7
>10000	34	13.8
1000—5000	105	42.5
Total	247	100.0

Table No.5: Monthly income wise distribution of participants

Monthly Income in Rs	Number of participants	Percentage
No income	47	19.0

Bar diagram represents monthly income wise distribution of participants

Figure no 5: Bar diagram represents monthly income wise distribution of participants

II.Data related to Knowledge

The following table and figure illustrate regarding scoring patterns for Knowledge, Attitude and Practice.

Table No.6: Pre-test knowledge score of participants

Pre-test knowledge scores	Categories	No. of participants	Percentage
---------------------------	------------	---------------------	------------

<50%	Poor	114	46.2
50%--75%	Moderately Good	110	44.5
75%--100%	Good	23	9.3
Total	---	247	100.0
Mean ± SD	4.78 ± 1.92 (47.8%)		

Bar diagram represents pre-test knowledge score of participants

Figure no 6: Bar diagram represents pre-test knowledge score of participants

Table No.7: Post-test knowledge score of participants

Pre-test knowledge scores	Categories	No. of participants	Percentage
---------------------------	------------	---------------------	------------

75%--100%	Good	96	38.9
Total	---	247	100.0
Mean ± SD	6.51 ± 2.07 (65.1%)		

Bar diagram represents post-test knowledge score of participants

Figure no 7: Bar diagram represents post-test knowledge score of participants

Table No.8: Comparison of knowledge scores of self-medication between Pre and Post-test

knowledge scores	Categories	Pre-test		Post-test	
		No.	%	No	%
<50%	Poor	114	46.2	46	18.6
50%--75%	Moderately Good	110	44.5	105	42.5
75%--100%	Good	23	9.3	96	38.9
Total	---	247	100.0	247	100.0
Mean \pm SD	----	4.78 \pm 1.92		6.51 \pm 2.07	
Diff. of mean	---	1.73 (36.19%)			
Paired t-test and p-value	t = 10.508, P = 0.0001, HS				

NS= not significant, S=significant, HS=highly significant

Multiple bar diagram shows the comparison of knowledge score of self-medication between Pre and Post-test

Figure no 8: Multiple bar diagram shows the comparison of knowledge score of self-medication between Pre and Post-test

III. Data related to Attitude

The response of the participants related to attitude were recorded and tabulated

Table No.9: Pre-test attitude of self-medication among rural population

Statements	Options	Number of participants	Percentage
1. Self-medications can be advised to others?	a) Agree	85	34.3
	b) Disagree	162	65.7
2. Do you think you will get desired relief from self-medications?	a) Agree	132	53.4
	b) Disagree	115	46.6
3. Self-medications under professional advice will give better out come?	a) Agree	112	45.3
	b) Disagree	135	54.7
4. Some of the drugs which are preferred as self-medications are not safe in pregnancy?	a) Agree	137	55.5
	b) Disagree	110	44.5
5. Self-medications are not safe all age groups?	a) Agree	86	34.8
	b) Disagree	161	65.2
6. Advice for self-medications can be taken from others?	a) Agree	84	34.0
	b) Disagree	163	66.0
7. Would you recommend self-medications to others for similar conditions you have treated yourself?	a) Agree	108	43.7
	b) Disagree	139	56.3
8. Do you think public awareness about the risk self-medications is sufficient?	a) Agree	96	38.9
	b) Disagree	151	61.1
9. Do you believe self-medications often with necessary due to lack of immediate access	a) Agree	125	50.6
	b) Disagree	122	49.4
10. Do you think that self-medication is a practical solution in today's busy life style?	a) Agree	112	45.3
	b) Disagree	135	54.7

Table No.10: Post-test attitude of self-medication among rural population

Statements	Options	Number of participants	Percentage
1. Self-medications can be advised to others?	a) Agree	61	24.7
	a) Disagree	186	75.3
2. Do you think you will get desired relief from self-medications?	a) Agree	114	46.2
	b) Disagree	133	53.8
3. Self-medications under professional advice will give better out come?	a) Agree	184	74.5
	b) Disagree	63	25.5
4. Some of the drugs which are preferred as self-medications are not safe in pregnancy?	a) Agree	182	73.7
	b) Disagree	65	26.3
5. Self-medications are not safe all age groups?	a) Agree	149	60.3
	b) Disagree	98	39.7
6. Advice for self-medications can be taken from others?	a) Agree	70	28.4
	b) Disagree	177	71.6
7. Would you recommend self-medications to others for similar conditions you have treated yourself?	a) Agree	85	34.4
	b) Disagree	162	65.6
8. Do you think public awareness about the risk self-medications is sufficient?	a) Agree	75	30.4
	b) Disagree	172	69.6
9. Do you believe self-medications often with necessary due to lack of immediate access	a) Agree	161	65.2
	b) Disagree	86	34.8
	a) Agree	174	70.4

10. Do you think that self-medication is a practical solution in today's busy life style?	b) Disagree	73	29.6
---	-------------	----	------

Table No.11: Comparison of attitude of self-medication among rural population (participants) between pre and post-test

Statements	Options	Number of participants		X ² test value P-value & sig
		Pre	Post	
1. Self-medications can be advised to others?	a) Agree	85	61	X ² = 5.600 P= 0.017, S
	b) Disagree	162	186	
2. Do you think you will get desired relief from self-medications?	a) Agree	132	114	X ² = 2.623 P= 0.105, NS
	b) Disagree	115	133	
3. Self-medications under professional advice will give better out come?	a) Agree	112	184	X ² = 43.695 P= 0.001, HS
	b) Disagree	135	63	
4. Some of the drugs which are preferred as self-medications are not safe in pregnancy?	a) Agree	137	182	X ² = 17.910 P= 0.001, HS
	b) Disagree	110	65	
5. Self-medications are not safe all age groups?	a) Agree	86	149	X ² = 32.213 P= 0.001, HS
	b) Disagree	161	98	
6. Advice for self-medications can be taken from others?	a) Agree	84	70	X ² = 1.849 P= 0.178, NS
	b) Disagree	163	177	
7. Would you recommend self-medications to others for similar conditions you have treated yourself?	a) Agree	108	85	X ² = 4.498 P= 0.033, S
	b) Disagree	139	162	
8. Do you think public awareness about the risk self-medications is sufficient?	a) Agree	96	75	X ² = 3.994 P= 0.047, S
	b) Disagree	151	172	
9. Do you believe self-medications often with necessary due to lack of immediate access	a) Agree	125	161	X ² = 10.762 P= 0.001, HS
	b) Disagree	122	86	
10. Do you think that self-medication is a practical solution in today's busy life style?	a) Agree	112	174	X ² = 31.921 P= 0.001, HS
	b) Disagree	135	73	

IV. Data related to Practice

The response of the participants related to practice were recorded and tabulated.

Table No.12: Pre-test practice of self-medication among rural population

Statements	Options	Number of participants	Percentage
1. Where did you obtain medicine for self-medication?	a) Community pharmacy	54	21.9
	b) Medical representative	99	40.1
	c) Left over previous prescription	51	20.6
	d) Others	43	17.4
2. For which of the following complaint did you use medicine?	a) Running nose	82	33.2
	b) Fever	65	26.3
	c) Aches and pain	43	17.4
	d) All of the above	57	23.1
3. How many time did you treat yourself with medication in past one year?	a) 1 time	69	27.9
	b) 2—5 times	79	32.0
	c) 6—10 times	57	23.1
	d) More than 10 times	35	14.2
	a) Cost saving	33	13.4

4. What are the reasons for using self-medication?	b) Convenience	69	27.9
	c) Lack of trust in prescribing	61	24.7
	d) Others	72	29.1
5. Your selection of medicine for self-treatment was based on?	a) Opinion of family and friends	50	20.2
	b) By own experience	81	32.8
	c) Previous doctor prescription	48	19.4
	d) Advertisement in mass-Medea	53	21.5
6. Do you check expiring date before taking self-medication?	a) Yes	53	21.5
	b) No	75	30.4
	c) Don't know	61	24.7
	d) Not sure	40	16.2
7. Do you store medication?	a) Always	69	27.9
	b) Often	69	27.9
	c) Sometimes	57	23.1
	d) Never	36	14.6
8. Do you keep the stock of medicine rather than the medicine prescribed by the doctors?	a) Always	39	15.8
	b) Often	81	32.8
	c) Sometimes	60	24.3
	d) Never	41	16.6
9. In all type of illness do you prefer self-medication?	a) Always	53	21.5
	b) Often	76	30.8
	c) Sometimes	57	23.1
	d) Never	45	18.2
10. Do you inform your healthcare provider all the medication your taking, including those for self-med	a) Always	96	38.9
	b) Often	40	16.2
	c) Sometimes	36	14.6
	d) Never	59	23.9

Table No.13: Post-test practice of self-medication among rural population

Statements	Options	Number of participants	Percentage
1. Where did you obtain medicine for self-medication?	a) Community pharmacy	54	21.9
	b) Medical representative	99	40.1
	c) Left over previous prescription	51	20.6
	d) Others	34	13.8
2. For which of the following complaint did you use medicine?	a) Running nose	104	42.1
	b) Fever	45	18.2
	c) Aches and pain	44	17.8
	d) All of the above	50	20.2
3. How many times did you treat yourself with medication in past one year?	a) 1 time	109	44.1
	b) 2—5 times	52	21.1
	c) 6—10 times	28	11.3
	d) More than 10 times	18	7.3
4. What are the reasons for using self-medication?	a) Cost saving	44	17.8
	b) Convenience	92	37.2
	c) Lack of trust in prescribing	44	17.8
	d) Others	52	21.1
5. Your selection of medicine for self-treatment was based on?	a) Opinion of family and friends	45	18.2
	b) By own experience	62	25.1
	c) Previous doctor prescription	61	24.7
	d) Advertisement in mass-Medea	47	19.0

6. Do you check expiring date before taking self-medication?	a) Yes	96	38.9
	b) No	52	21.2
	c) Don't 'know	45	18.2
	d) Not sure	38	15.4
7. Do you store medication?	a) Always	57	23.1
	b) Often	71	28.7
	c) Sometimes	70	28.3
	d) Never	28	11.3
8. Do you keep the stock of medicine rather than the medicine prescribed by the doctors?	a) Always	39	15.8
	b) Often	66	26.7
	c) Sometimes	61	24.7
	d) Never	53	21.5
9. In all type of illness do you prefer self-medication?	a) Always	45	18.2
	b) Often	74	30.0
	c) Sometimes	57	23.1
	d) Never	48	19.4
10. Do you inform your healthcare provider all the medication your taking, including those for self-med	a) Always	106	42.9
	b) Often	43	17.4
	c) Sometimes	31	12.6
	d) Never	44	17.8

Table No.14: Comparison of practice of self-medication among rural population (participants) between pre and post-test

Statements	Options	Pre-test	Post-test	X ² test P-value
1. Where did you obtain medicine for self-medication?	a) Community pharmacy	54	54	X ² = 0.885 P= 0.828, NS
	b) Medical representative	99	99	
	c) Left previous prescription	51	51	
	d) Others	43	34	
2. For which of the following complaint did you use medicine?	a) Running nose	82	104	X ² = 6.969 P= 0.043, S
	b) Fever	65	45	
	c) Aches and pain	43	44	
	d) All of the above	57	50	
3. How many times did you treat yourself with medication in past one year?	a) 1 time	69	109	X ² = 27.615 P= 0.001, HS
	b) 2—5 times	79	52	
	c) 6—10 times	57	28	
	d) More than 10 times	35	18	
4. What are the reasons for using self-medicating?	a) Cost saving	33	44	X ² = 10.814 P= 0.012, S
	b) Convenience	69	92	
	c) Lack of trust in prescribe	61	44	
	d) Others	72	52	
5. Your selection of medicine for self-treatment was based on?	a) Opinion of family & friends.	50	45	X ² = 4.057 P= 0.255, NS
	b) By own experience	81	62	
	c) Previous prescription	48	61	
	d) Advertisement & media	53	47	
6. Do you check expiring date before taking self-medication?	a) Yes	53	96	X ² = 19.037 P= 0.001, HS
	b) No	75	52	
	c) Don't 'know	61	45	
	d) Not sure	40	38	

7. Do you store medication?	a) Always	69	57	X ² = 3.448 P= 0.327, NS
	b) Often	69	71	
	c) Sometimes	57	70	
	d) Never	36	28	
8. Do you keep the stock of medicine rather than the medicine prescribed by the doctors?	a) Always	39	39	X ² = 3.061 P= 0.382, NS
	b) Often	81	66	
	c) Sometimes	60	61	
	d) Never	41	53	
9. In all type of illness do you prefer self-medication?	a) Always	53	45	X ² = 0.765 P= 0.874, NS
	b) Often	76	74	
	c) Sometimes	57	57	
	d) Never	45	48	
10. Do you inform your healthcare provider all the medication your taking, including those for self-med	a) Always	96	106	X ² = 3.054 P= 0.383, NS
	b) Often	40	43	
	c) Sometimes	36	31	
	d) Never	59	44	

Statistical data analysis: Statistical data was analyzed by IBM SPSS 25.0 version software. Collected data were spread on excel sheet and prepared master chart. Through the master chart tables and graphs were constructed. For qualitative data analysis chi-square test and Fisher exact tests were applied. For quantitative data analysis t-test and ANOVA tests were applied for statistical significance. If P-value was less than 0.05 considered as significant.

DISCUSSION

Self-Medication is more likely to be inappropriate if used by poorly informed people. The depth of knowledge regarding self-medication use in rural community is need to be assessed. Many of the individuals often practice self-medication for various medical illnesses. Even though self-medication is useful to treat mild to moderate illness, improper self-medication may lead to ADR's and drug interactions. In our study we have enrolled 247 participants out of which male 145 (58.7%) were more compared to female 102 (41.3%) which was identical to the study conducted by Ahmad A et al.²¹ We have categorized the participants age into 4 groups of 20

years interval each comprising of 21-40 years in 113 (45.8%) followed by 41-60 years include 83 (33.6%) ≤ 20 years include 26 (10.5%) and only 25 (10.1%) belonged to the age group of 61-80 years which was in concurrence with the study conducted by Sivaskthi k et al. In rural areas of Erode.²⁴ Most of the subject's occupation of our study was labours 64 (25.9%), followed by farmers 49 (19.8%), job holders 45 (18.2%), house wife 40 (16.2%) and only 18 (7.3%) were unemployed which was similar to the study conducted by Thuzar Moe et al.³⁰ In our study most of them were married 175 (70.9%) and 72 (29.1%) were unmarried which is similar to the study conducted by Limaye D et al.⁹ Most of the participants income of our study was 105 (42.5%) were does not showed the income i-e nil income, 61 (25.7%) of participant's monthly income in the range of 6000—10000, 47 (19.0%) of participant's monthly income was in the range of 1000—5000 and 34 (13.8%) of participant's monthly income was >10000, which was identical to the study conducted by Shafie M et al.²⁹ As we analyzed in the present study the mean knowledge scores of participants in pre-test and post-test was 4.78 and 6.51 which was identical to the study conducted by MD Sohail A et al.³¹ In according to our study, we

designed 10 questions of Attitude. During pre-test in Attitude related questionnaire 137 (55.5%) participants felt self-medication are not safe in pregnancy. These findings are similar to the study conducted self-medication among pharmacy students by F Susheela et al.⁶ In pretest 86 (34.8%) and post 149 (60.3%) majority are not safe in all age group. These findings are identical to the study conducted by the F. Susheela et al. on self-medication among students in pharmacy.⁶ In according to our study, we designed 10 questions of practice. Most of the participants are said Yes 53 (21.5%) in pre-test, after interval 96 (38.9%), Majority of the participants has changed their practice towards checking of expiring date of self-medication which was concurrent to the study conducted by Uppal D et al.²⁶ Thus, the health education on self-medication given to the rural population was found to be significantly effective. As an outcome, our study revealed that majority of the population were unaware about proper usage of self-medication. It brings various risks when these medicines are not taken accordingly.

CONCLUSION

- Our study findings revealed that the rural population have insufficient knowledge regarding self-medication.
- In our study the rural respondents were in the opinion that self-medication is not safe in all age groups and few of them felt self-medication is not safe in pregnancy.
- Another important aspect of our study appreciates that rural population had the habit of asking the chemist to check the expiry date before using the medications.
- The outcomes have shown that educational intervention has significant impact on knowledge, attitude and practice of self-

medication among rural population. Community pharmacists have pivotal role in providing information about the medications to patients.

- After educational intervention the knowledge, attitude and practice regarding self-medication were significantly improved.

REFERENCES

1. Marak A, Borah M, Bhattacharyya H, Talukdar K, A cross-sectional study on self-medication practices among the rural population of Meghalaya, *Int J of Med Sci and Public Health*, 2016; 5(6): 1134 – 1138
2. Cecyli C, Pragati T. Assessment of knowledge and practice of self-medication among urban and rural population. *DIT*, 2020; 13(6): 1059-64.
3. Kumari R, Kumar D, Bahl R, Gupta R, Study of Knowledge and Practices of Self - medication among Medical Students at Jammu, *J of Med Sci*, 2012; 15(2): 141-14
4. Kalyani V, Bisht M, Thapliyal S, Rohilla KK. Comparison of practice and attitude of self-treatment in rural and urban population in Uttarakhand, India: A comparative study. *NJPPP*. 2020; 10(12): 1052-9.
5. Gayathri S, Selvaraj K, Satyajith P, Mithunkumar G.H, Estimation of self - medication practices among rural Kanchipuram, India, *Research Article IAIM*, 2017; 4(10): 87-92
6. Susheela F, Goruntla N, Bhupalam PK, Veerabhadrapa KV, Sahithi B, Ishrar SM. Assessment of knowledge, attitude, and practice toward responsible self-medication among students of pharmacy colleges located in Anantapur district, Andhra Pradesh, India. *JEHP*. 2018; 7:96;1-8.
7. Thoufiq AAA, Vijayan A. Prevalence of self-medication practices in Urban area of

- Kanchipuram district, Tamil Nadu. IJCMPH,2020;7(3):1089-94.
8. Jalihalkar S.S, Birari P.B, Gaykhe A, Mishal RH, Mishal HB. Self-medication among pharmacy students – A threatening trend. IJMPR,2020;4(3):126-130.
 9. Limaye D, Limaye V, Fortwengel G, Krause G. Self-medication practices in urban and rural areas of western India: a cross-sectional study. IJCMPH. 2018;(5 (7)):2672-85.
 10. Latifi A, Ramezankhani A, Rezaei Z, Ashtarian H, Salmani B, Yousefi MR, Khezeli M. Prevalence and associated factors of self-medication among the college students in Tehran. JAPS. 2017 Jul;7(7):128-32.
 11. Prasad BS, Chouhan K. Self-medication and their consequences: A challenge to health professional. AJPCR,2016;9(2):314-317.
 12. Patil BS, Nagaiah HB, Raikar RS, Rao V. Self-medication practices among 2nd year medical students in a rural medical college of Telangana state. NJPPP,2018;8(4):501-506.
 13. Mehta R K, Sharma S, Knowledge, Attitude and Practice of Self-Medication among Medical Students, IOSR J Of Nursing and Health Science, 2015; 4(1): 89-96
 14. James H, H.A.J Khalid, Al Khaja Sameer Ootom Reginald P. Sequeira, Evaluation of the Knowledge, Attitude and Practice of Self-Medication among First-Year Medical Students, Med Princ Pract, 2006; 15: 270-275
 15. Chordiya S V. Role of pharmacist in rational drug therapy. IP J of Surgery and Allied Sci, 2019 Mar;1(1):5-7.
 16. Singh NP, Singh N, Jain PK, Singh V, Chaurasiya S, Verma R, Ranjan M. Comparative study to determine self-medication practice and pattern in urban and rural areas of Etawah district. IJCMPH, 2019; 7[1]; 216-223.
 17. Vidyavati SD, Sneha A, Kamarudin J, Katti SM. Self-medication-reasons, risks and benefits. IJHBR. 2016 Jul;4(04):4.21-24.
 18. Karmacharya A, Uprety BN, Pathiyil RS, Gyawali S. Knowledge and practice of self-medication among undergraduate medical students. JLMC. 2018 May 13;6(1):21-6.
 19. Sinha U, Namdev G. Knowledge attitude and practices among self-medication users in a rural area of Bhopal NJCM, 2016; 7(10); 825-828.
 20. Makeen HA, Albarraq AA, Banji OJ, Taymour S, Meraya A, Alqhatani S, Banji D. Knowledge, attitudes, and practices toward self-medication in a rural population in South-Western Saudi Arabia. SJHS. 2019 Jan 1;8(1):54.
 21. Ahmad A, Khan MU, Srikanth AB, Kumar B, Singh NK, Trivedi N, Elnour AA, Patel I. Evaluation of knowledge, attitude and practice about self-medication among rural and urban north Indian population. IJPCR. 2015 Oct 25;7(05):326-32.
 22. Swetha R, Rani U. Study of self-medication pattern among adults in Tumkur city. JPMHH. 2021 Feb 15;2(1):13-6.
 23. Athira R, Govind G, Irene MJ, Sachin C, Ritty SC, Vishwanath BA. Knowledge, Attitude and Practice towards Self-Medications in a Rural Community. JDDT. 2020 Jun 15;10(3- s):128-32.
 24. Sivasakthi K, Koshila KS, Viswa S. Assessment of Knowledge, Attitude and Practice about Self Medication among Rural Areas in Erode District. IJOPP. 2020;13(3).
 25. Singh A, Dhami DB, Singh K, Shah GJ. Self-medication practice among undergraduate medical students in Nepalgunj medical college, Chisapani. JNGMC,2018;16(1);67-70.
 26. Agarwal M, Uppal D, Roy V. Assessment of Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice of self-

- medication among college students. *IJBCP*,2014;3(6):988-994
27. Bhandari A, Upadhyay R, Joshi A, Bajeta D, Maher D, Joshi J, Singh K, Bisht N, Misha N, Bisht R, Haldar P, Peter R, Bisht M. Self-medication practices in nursing students. *IJSHR*,2018;3(2):35-39.
 28. Syed N, Naseer M, Memon MQ, Rani K. Prevalence of self-medication and its practice among the medical and non-medical students. *JLUMHS*. 2014 May;13(02):79.
 29. Shafie M, Eyasu M, Muzeyin K, Worku. Prevalence and determinants of self-medication practice among selected households in Addis Ababa community.2016; doi: 10.1371/journal.phone.0194122.t003
 30. Thuzar M, Aung P. Prevalence of self-medication and its influence in the labour force in Rural Hlaing Tharyar, Yangon, Myanmar. *The Open Public Health J*, 2019: DOI 10.2174/1874944501912010038.
 31. MD Sohail A, Ghanti N, Regi M, Thombre N, Waggi M. A study on knowlwge, attitude and practice about self medication among rural population of Kalaburagi city. *World J of pharmaceutical Res*.2022 jul ; 11(12):2037-2045.

HOW TO CITE: Bhosale Abhilekh*, Patti Sri Harsha Vardhan, Siddaling Phoolar, Sagar Reddy, Vishwanath M. Jeevangi, A Study on Knowledge, Attitude and Practice About Self-Medication Among Rural Population of Kalaburagi District, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, Vol 3, Issue 10, 2514-2530 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17430492>

